

EVALUATION OF ANGUWA SARAKUNA SOIL STABILIZED WITH CEMENT USING LOCUST BEAN POD SOLUTION AS SUB-GRADE MATERIAL IN ROAD CONSTRUCTION

Cyprian Stephen¹, Sa'eed Yusuf Umar², & Suleiman Arafat Yero³

^{1, 2, & 3}Department of Civil Engineering, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: jacystephen43@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15056383>

ABSTRACT

A soil sample was collected from Anguwa Sarakuna in Bauchi metropolis at a depth of 1–1.2 m using a disturbed method with a digger and shovel. The purpose was to evaluate stabilization using cement combined with locust bean pod solution (LBPS) as subgrade material for road construction. The natural soil was analyzed for its chemical and geotechnical properties and divided into control and stabilized groups. Tests conducted included preliminary soil investigation, compaction, and California Bearing Ratio (CBR). Results showed that the soil was classified as A-7-6 (9) by AASHTO and as SC (clayey sand) per USCS, with an Ss ratio of 3.2 confirming its non-lateritic nature. LBPS exhibited a pH of 6.5, reddish-brown colour, and was categorized as Class C pozzolana. The Dangote Portland cement used had a soundness of 1.1, initial and final setting times of 73 and 193 minutes respectively, a fineness of 0.03, consistency of 30%, and a specific gravity of 3.02. The control and stabilized samples recorded MDD values between 1.93 and 1.97–1.87 Mg/m³ and OMC values from 15.9 to 20.0%. CBR values for both soaked and unsoaked conditions met NFMWH requirements. Finally, the developed model demonstrated a significant relationship between LBPS and stabilized soil performance.

Keywords: LBPS, Stabilization, Cement, Subgrade, Soil

INTRODUCTION

The level of development in north-eastern Nigeria has necessitate the increase in construction work in engineering projects such as road in rural areas resulting to the increase in exploitation of natural resources such as lateritic soil. Lateritic soil is characterised by low bearing capacity and strength, largely attributed to their elevated clay content. The high clay content present in the soil can lead to a substantial decline in its stability and strength when subjected to loading, particularly in environment where moisture is present. The inherent composition of lateritic soils which includes high plasticity clay minerals, can lead to the development of cracks as a result of the soil's plastic behaviours and damage on the pavement, roadway, foundation or any civil engineering structure under construction (Nnochiri & Aderinlewo, 2016). Engineers in developing countries are confronted with the difficulties of locating suitable material for subgrade in engineering works. Soil in nature states varies in properties in place and location. The inconsistency in the nature and properties of laterites is essential for sustainability of road network.

Stabilisation refer to as a process of soil modification entails intentionally altering the characteristics of in in-situ soil through one or more of the following methods: blending or mixing with other soil or materials to enhance particle size distribution, or incorporating additive to achieve the desired engineering properties, thereby meeting specific project specification and requirement. In the context of road construction, soil stabilisation is a deliberate process undertaken to develop the engineering properties of the subgrade soil, and capacity to withstand the imposed loads and stresses from the pavement and traffic; improvement in volumetric stability –undesirable properties such as shrinkage, swelling, challenges in compaction and high plasticity characteristic brings about change in moisture and improvement in durability bring about increase erosion resistance, weathering and traffic, improvement of poor workability, high permeability, and frost susceptibility among other. Thus, when choosing stabilising agent certain factors are put into consideration such as: soil type, stabilization goal, quality of the soil stabilised, the strength and durability properties of stabilized layer, environment condition and cost of stabilisation (Fitsum, 2018).

The use of Agricultural waste products that are left after the fruit had been consumed Such as; Rice husk, groundnut husk, corn comb, palm kernel shell, saw dust, baggers, banana peels, neem seed husk, cassava peel, shear nut shell etc. Are recently invoke for research in the field of geotechnical engineering, however, emphasis is being made on the search for cheaper and locally made available materials for the purposes of stabilisation and a huge percentage of such materials are gotten from agriculture waste, which possess cementitious properties on exposure to moisture (Ige & Oyeniyen, 2018).

Discovery has shown that around Plateau, Niger, Kaduna and Bali local government area of Taraba state, locust bean pod extract is used on walls built with lateritic soil and floor of rooms. However, this forms the premises of this research on the effect of this solution on the strength of lateritic soil for subgrade since many emphasis has been laid on the ash and the finding has demonstrate how efficient the locust pod can be, so also on the extract which serves as finish to the internal and external walls of buildings made of lateritic soil such as during the raining season, the extract percolate into the walls from the husk then increasing the strength of the structure in the process. So also, the binding properties exhibited by the extract in the traditional construction processes described above and other waste of locust bean such as the ash which possesses pozzolanic properties triggered the quest for the research work on it effect on subgrade for road construction on that note this research is on the extract to see how effective it will be on subgrade.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The growth rate and development level, especially in rural area in Nigeria has triggered much demand for roadway and infrastructure facilities. Most times the soil available are unsuitable in terms of strength requirement to meet the engineering purpose for construction. Furthermore, the perpetual fluctuation in the prices of both cement and aggregate has made it difficult for the government to meet the demands of the masses. Thus, it is important for engineers to look at alternative means to improve the soil other than replacing the poor soil on site. Therefore, this study was developed to bridge this gap by testing the effects of locust bean pod extract on non-lateritic soil as a medium of soil improvement in construction sites.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study aims at evaluating Anguwa Sarakuna soil stabilized with cement using locust bean pod solution as sub-grade material in road construction. However, the study specifically seeks;

- i. To characterize the Soil and Locust Bean Pod Extract (LBPE)
- ii. To investigate the potential of Locust Bean Pod Extract (LBPE) and Cement for stabilization of Non-Lateritic Soil

- iii. To develop a model for prediction of California bearing ratio (CBR)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample preparation: the sample was prepared in to categories of control and cement stabilised soil of locust bean pod solution at 0, 2, 4, 6, and 8% replacement of water by weight and cement is kept constant at 2%, the concentration of the LBPS 0.4kg/l, pH Value of 6.5 and the sample of the Locust bean pod was soaked for a duration of 5days.

Materials

a. Soil:

The soil sample collected was via disturbed sampling technique with the aids of digger, shovel and sack, from a borrow pit situated at Anguwa sarakuna along Maiduguri road Bauchi metropolis. The soil sample was collected at depths range 1 - 1.2 m. The samples, were collected in sack bags and conveyed to the geotechnical/soil mechanics Laboratory of the Department of Civil Engineering Technology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. The samples were air-dried, large lumps crushed and passed through BS No. 4 sieve (4.75 mm aperture).

b. Locust bean pod extract:

The locust bean pod sample was collected from Bali local government area of Taraba state, the sample was collected in large sacks due to its abundant nature around the area and its availability, was transported to the laboratory for the research work.

c. Cement:

The Dangote ordinary Portland cement was obtained from yelwa tundu market in Bauchi metropolis and conveyed to Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University laboratory, Bauchi

d. Water:

The water used for the research was fetched from the waterworks Abubakar Tafawa Balewa university Bauchi.

METHODOLOGY

The preliminary investigation for research was carried out in accordance to BS 1377:1990. ASTM D2487-11 and ASTM D3282-09. Specification for soil test and XRF for oxide composition. For the research material were basically non-lateritic soil sample, locust bean pod extract and cement which were mixed at different proportion in accordance to their percentage design for research purpose. The cement was kept at 2% constant and the locust bean pod extract which was a liquid admixture was used at 0, 2, 4, 6 and 8% replacement by weight of water. Thus, the sample were confined to the following laboratory test: compaction and California bearing ratio CBR (for both soaked and un-soaked condition).

Compaction Characteristics

The British standard light (BSL) compaction technique was implemented for this study. The test was carried out according to BS 1377-1990, with the aim of determining the maximum dry density MDD and optimum moisture content OMC of the soils and stabilized sample. Preliminary to compaction, the soil mixtures were thoroughly blended to ensure uniform distribution of the additives subsequently, a comprehensive compaction testing program was undertaken, comprising two distinct phases. The first phase focused on determining the compaction properties of the untreated natural soil samples

and the second phase involves the evaluating the compaction properties of the soil sample upon stabilisation with constant cement 2% and varying proportion of locust bean pod extract (LBPE), specifically 2, 4, 6 and 8%.

California bearing ratio (CBR)

The BS 1377-1990 stipulates the procedures to follow in carrying out this test. This, was however modified in conformity with the recommendation of the Nigerian General Specification, Federal Ministry of Works and Housing,

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Oxide composition of soil and locust bean pod solution

The presented explain in brief the summary result from the text conducted on the natural soil and stabilized soil sample

Table 1: Summary Result of Oxide Composition for soil at Anguwa Sarakuna

Oxide	Percentage concentration
SiO ₂	64.092
Fe ₂ O ₃	8.872
Al ₂ O ₃	11.299

From the table 1 above and 2 below, the total sum by weight percentage composition of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃, which is 64.092%, 11.299% and 8.872%, $S_s = \frac{SiO_2}{(Fe_2O_3 + Al_2O_3)} = 3.177$ which is greater than 2 therefore classified the soil to be non-lateritic in nature

Table 2: Table of conformity for soil classification

Names	Sesquioxide ratio
Laterite	1.33
Lateritic	1.33 - 2.00
Non-lateritic	2.0

Source: Enaworu et al. (2017)

Laterite are a type of soil that forms through the weathering of rocks in tropical regions, resulting in a characteristic reddish-brown to dark brown coloration. They may exhibit nodules or concretions and are typically found beneath a hardened ferruginous crust or hardpan. The classification of laterites is based on the ratio of silica to sesquioxide (SiO₂/Fe O₃ + Al₂ O₃), which is used to distinguished between categories: laterite (ratio< 1.33), lateritic (ratio1.33-2.0), and non-lateritic(ratio>2.0).

Table 3: Oxide Composition of cement and Locust Bean Pod Extract

Element	Cement OPC %	CONC (%) LBPE
Na ₂ O	-	0.91
MgO	1.84	1.03
Al ₂ O ₃	5.29	10.21
SiO ₂	21.52	41.97
P ₂ O ₅	-	2.05
CaO	64.46	9.75
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.95	2.0
SO ₃	1.50	-

Source: Duru et al. (2020)

The percentage composition of SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃, is approximately 54% which belong to class C. For a stabilising agent to be classified as a pozzolanic material, it must demonstrate the ability to undergo a pozzolanic reaction, wherein it combines with calcium hydroxide to produce cementitious compounds that contribute to the stabilization and strengthen of the soil. (Duru *et al*, 2020; ASTM C618- 92a-1994).

Table 4: Index Properties of the Natural Soil before Stabilization

Characteristics	Description
Natural moisture contents (%)	24.1
Specific Gravity(G _s)	2.74
Liquid Limit (W _L) (%)	41
Plastic Limit (P _L) (%)	25.6
Plasticity Index (P _i) (%)	15.4
Linear shrinkage (P _L) (%)	13
Maximum Dry Density (MDD) (Mg/m ³)	1.93
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) (%)	11.3
AASHTO Classification	A-7-6(9)
USCS Classification	SC
CBR soaked (%)	29.4
CBR un-soaked (%)	38.9
Color	Grey

Result on Particle Size Distribution

The results obtained from the Particle size distribution and physical properties of the soil are presented in figure 1. Thus, classified soil as A-7-6 (9) in accordance with the American association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO M 145-2012) soil classification system with the group index of 9 which falls within the range of poor condition of subgrade soil thus, help to show the difference between the quality of soil within certain group. And SC (SAND-Clayey) in accordance with the Unified Soil Classification System (ASTM D 2487-2011) respectively. The average values of the liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index were 41, 25 and 15.4 respectively, while the linear shrinkage is 13, coefficient of uniformity Cu = 4 and coefficient of curvature Cc= 1. The figure 1 and plate 1 shows the particle size distribution curve as well as the wet sieving approach used to achieve the sieve analysis.

Figure 1: Particle Size Distribution Graph

Plate 1: Hydrometer sieving

Compaction

From the figures 2 and 3, the MDD and OMC from the compaction test conducted for British standard light (BSL) compactions from a height of 300m, 27 numbers of blows and 3 layers. The result obtained are 1.73 Mg/m³ and 15.9 % for light compaction.

Figure 2: BSL Compaction 2.5kg rammer 300mm height

Figure 3: Maximum Dry Density and Optimum Moisture Content 2.5kg Rammer

Similarly to the case of the stabilized soil with 2% cement and 0%, 2%, 4%, 6% and 8% replacement of water with locust bean pod extract. The MDD and OMC are BSL 1.59, 1.64, 1.64, 1.67 and 1.68 Mg/m³ and 15.9, 16.2, 17.6, 18.4 and 20 % respectively. Figure 3 shows that as the MDD decreases with in LBPS, the OMC on the other hand increases with increase in the LBPS.

California Bearing Ratio

Figure 4: California Bearing Ratio Graph

From figure 4, the CBR value obtained for the controls and the stabilized soil ranges from 8.3 to 38.9% and 9.8 to 29.4% for both un-soaked and soaked condition. The result indicates that at 2.5mm and 5.0mm penetration there is general increase in the CBR value from the control with 2% cement 0%LBPE up to 6 and 8% LBPE with 29.4 and 38.9% higher value for both penetrations as compared with the other of 9.4, 19.4, 19.8% and 22% for the case of soaked and for the un-soaked 20.7, 20.9, 28.9 and 29.1%. 6% and 8% LBPE, gives a better result when compared with other penetration. Thus, in conformity with soil material to be use as sub-grade which is expected to fulfil a maximum value of 30% and 60% for PI and LL values, respectively and a minimum CBR value of 5%, a swell of 2% is the maximum requirement for the standard

manuals (ERA, 2002). In this regards the CBR value for both the un-soaked and soaked condition for both BSL satisfies the requirement for sub-grade in agreement with Nigeria Federal Ministry of Work and Housing (NFMWH).

Regression model for Soaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR) Condition

From the result obtained for the CBR soaked condition, a regression analysis model was run to investigate the effective of locust bean pod extract on cement stabilized soil as subgrade for road construction. The model equation is given as

$$S-CBR_L = 11.48 + 2.130 LBPE \quad \dots 1$$

Where:

The terms β_0 and β_1 are the parameters of the model. The parameter

β_0 is termed as intercept/ constant term 18.04

β_1 is termed as slope parameter 2.780LBPE

y is termed as the dependent or study or response CBR (%)

x is termed as independent or explanatory variable % replacement 0,2,4,6 and 8%

From the regression model developed, the LBPE has significant impact on cement stabilized soil. The independent variable which is LBPE was regressed for predicting variable of the California Bearing Ratio for the stabilized soil in a soaked condition. LBPE significantly predicted cement stabilized soil $F(2= 23.03) p < 0.05$ which indicated that LBPE has played a significant role in shaping cement stabilized soil ($b=2.130, p < 0.05$) therefore, the results clarify direct the positive effect of the LBPE, moreover, the $R^2 = .885$ for the models explains that 88.5% of the variance for soaked.

Figure 5: Residual Plot for Un-soaked California Bearing Ratio to Locust Bean Pod Extract on Cement Stabilized Non-Lateritic Soil

Regression Model for Un-Soaked California Bearing Ratio (CBR) Condition

The summary table which best explained the model is expressed in Equation 2.

$$U_n - CBR_L = 18.64 + 2.230 LBPE$$

... 2

The result of the model developed, the independent variable which is LBPE was regressed on predicting variable of California Bearing Ratio of the stabilized soil in an un-soaked condition.

Figure 6: Residual Plot for Soaked California Bearing Ratio to Locust Bean Pod Extract on Cement Stabilized Non-Lateritic Soil

LBPE significantly predicted cement stabilized soil $F(2= 24.99) p < 0.05$ which indicated that LBPE has played a significant role in shaping the cement stabilized soil ($b=2.230, p < 0.05$) therefore, the results clarified direct the positive effect of the LBPE. Moreover, the $R^2 = .8928$ of the models explained that 89.28% of the variance in unsoaked California Bearing Ratio condition of the stabilized soil at 2.5 and 5.0mm penetrations.

Sensitivity Analysis of the Model

The result from the relationship of the predicted value against the experimental values obtained for the soaked and un-soaked condition of the California bearing ratio (CBR) with locust bean pod extract (LBPE,) the coefficient of determination (R^2) based on the result from the model from the fit statistics based on the R^2 and R adjusted. If the difference is less than 0.2 which implies that the data have fitted well to the model chosen. The plot of the experimental against the predicted values are presented in figure 7-8.

Figure 7: Plot of Model Predicted Against Experiment for Soaked CBR condition BSL

Figure 8: Plot of Model Predicted Against Experiment Un-soaked CBR condition BSL

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were drawn as follows:

- i. The soil falls under the class of A-7- 6(9) and its SANDY- clayey (SC) in nature.
- ii. The MDD and OMC values are 1.68, 1.67, 1.64, 1.64 and 1.59 Mg/m³ and 15.9, 16.2, 17.6, 18.4 and 20 % respectively. Which infer that as the MDD increases the OMC tends to decrease.
- iii. The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) result for all the percentage replacement satisfies the requirement for subgrade and with the best result attained at 6 and 8% replacement of locust bean pod extract (LBPE) for both soaked and un-soaked condition in conformity with Nigeria Federal Ministry of Work and Housing (NFMWH).
- iv. The model was development to predict the CBR result and are such the effect of the locust bean pod extract. The result shows some great level of significance as the $P < 0.05$ and the coefficient of variance R^2 which range from 88.5-89.2 signifying that there is a reasonable degree of correlation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The potential of adding beyond 8% of LBPE on cement stabilized soil, since the present study indicated that at 6 and 8% replacement of locust bean pod extract (LBPE) by weight of water, there was a positive or appreciative response on the improvement of the soaked and unoaked CBR.

REFERENCES

- American Society for Testing and Materials. (1978). Specifications for pozzolans (ASTM C618). ASTM International.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (2003). Unified soil classification system (ASTM D2487-11). ASTM International.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (2003). Standard practice for classification of soils and soil aggregate mixture for highway construction purpose (ASTM D3282-09). ASTM International.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (2004). Standard test method for specific gravity of soil solids by water (ASTM D854-02). ASTM International.
- British Standards Institution. (1990). Methods of test for soils for civil engineering purposes (BS 1377-2). BSI.
- British Standards Institution. (1990). Methods of test for stabilized materials for civil engineering purposes (BS 1924: Part 2). BSI.
- British Standards Institution. (1996). Specification for Portland cements (BS 12). BSI.
- British Standards Institution. (2002). Mixing water for concrete: Specification for sampling testing and assessing the suitability of water (BS EN 1008). BSI.
- British Standards Institution. (2000). Cement: Composition, specifications, and conformity criteria for common cements (BS EN 197-1). BSI.
- Duru, P. P., Kaura, J. M., Akin, O. O., & Raymond, I. B. (2020). The compressive strength and water absorption properties of lateritic blocks stabilized with cement and locust bean pod extract. *International Journal of Advanced Geosciences*, 8(2), 186-192.
- Ethiopian Roads Authority. (2002). Pavement design manual volume I: Flexible pavement and gravel roads.
- Ethiopian Roads Authority. (2002). Site investigation manuals.
- Enaworu, E., Ugbe, F. C., Rotimi, O. J., & Ameloko, A. A. (2017). Geochemistry and geotechnical analysis of lateritic soils in the Anambra Basin. *Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*, 22(11), 4395-4413.
- Federal Ministry of Works & Housing. (1997). General specification for roads and bridges, volume II. Federal Highway Department, FMWH.
- Fitsum, M. D. (2018). Recent literature review on stabilization of laterite soil. *International Journal of Scientific Research Engineering and Technology (IJSTRET)*, 7(11).
- Ige, J. A., & Oyeniyani, W. O. (2018). A study on subgrade soil using locust bean pod waste ash as an admixture. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 9(3).
- Nnochiri, E. S., & Aderinlewo, O. O. (2016). Geotechnical properties of lateritic soil stabilized with banana leave ash. *FUOYE Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 1(1), 116-119.